

EOMORES

D3.4: Automated in situ instruments setup, prototype processors and products

WP3 – Innovative service component development

Authors: S. Peters, K. Poser

TARTU OBSERVATORY
space research centre

KLAIPĖDA
UNIVERSITY

UNIVERSITY of
STIRLING

Plymouth Marine
Laboratory

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730066.

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	730066	Acronym	EOMORES	
Full Title	Earth Observation-Based Services For Monitoring And Reporting Of Ecological Status			
Horizon 2020 Call	EO-1-2016: Downstream applications			
Type of Action	Innovation Action			
Start Date	01/12/2016	Duration	36 months	
Project URL	http://eomores-h2020.eu			
EU Project Officer	Iulia SIMION			
Project Coordinator	Water Insight BV			
Deliverable	D3.4: Automated in situ instruments setup, prototype processors and products			
Work Package	WP3 – Innovative service component development			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M24	Actual	M24
Nature	Other	Dissemination Level	Public	
Lead Beneficiary	Water Insight BV			
Lead Author	S. Peters	Email	Peters@waterinsight.nl	
	Water Insight BV	Phone	+31 6 41903163	
Other authors	K. Poser			
Reviewer(s)	Mark Warren, PML			
Keywords	in situ, optical measurements, WISPstation, services, automation			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1.0	2018-12-17	Version 1	First version	WI
2.0	2018-12-19	Version 2	Internal review	PML

How to cite this document:

Please use the following reference when citing this report:

Peters, Steef. 2018. D3.4: Automated in situ instruments setup, prototype processors and products, EOMORES Project Deliverable, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3987965.

Table of Contents

I. Introduction	5
II. Scope.....	5
III. The technical properties of the WISPstation instrument	5
IV. Database and output API.....	7
V. EOMORES demonstration installations of the WISPstation	8
V.1. WISPstation001: Lake Trasimeno, Italy	8
V.2. WISPstation003: Loch Leven, Schotland.....	9
V.3. WISPstation005: Lake Võrtsjärv, Estonia	9
V.4. WISPstation006 and 007: Curonian Lagoon, Lithuania	10
VI. Some preliminary results	11
VII. Summary of questionnaire results.....	17
VIII. Conclusions	18
References	19
IX. Annexes.....	20
IX.1. Annex I: Description of data queries through the API	20
IX.1.1. General requests.....	20
IX.1.2. Measurement fields	21
IX.1.3. Instrument fields.....	21
IX.1.4. Level 1 data	22
IX.1.5. Level 1B data.....	22
IX.1.6. Level 2 data	23
IX.1.7. Water quality parameters.....	23
IX.1.8. Filtering the request to space, time or instrument number.....	23

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Layout and installation of a WISPstation	6
Figure 2 Location information and photograph of WISPstation001.....	8
Figure 3 Location information and photograph of WISPstation003.....	9
Figure 4 Location information and photograph of WISPstation005.....	9
Figure 5 Location information and photograph of WISPstation006.....	10
Figure 6 typical spectra of WISPstation001	11
Figure 7: time series of standard water quality parameters at WISPstation001	11
Figure 8: time series of standard water quality parameters at WISPstation003	12
Figure 9: typical spectra at WISPstation005	13
Figure 10:time series of standard water quality parameters at WISPstation005	13

Figure 11: typical spectra at WISPstation006 15
Figure 12: time series of standard water quality parameters at WISPstation006 15
Figure 13: time series of water quality parameters at WISPstation007 16

Table of Tables

Table 1 Specifications of the WISPstation 7
Table 2 EOMORES installations of the WISPstations 8

I. Introduction

Within the framework of the EOMORES project in-situ optical sensors were installed and tested. The idea is that continuously registering optical sensors serve several purposes, of which the most important are:

- 1) Collect reference reflectance data during satellite overpasses to calibrate and validate satellite reflectances
- 2) Complement the satellite and modelling products in the EOMORES portfolio by providing high frequency point measurements of reflectance and derived water quality products

The fixed position optical in-situ sensors (WISPstations) were developed by Water Insight and five advanced prototype instruments were sent to local partners and placed at various locations during 2018. The data were collected autonomously and processed in near-real time by the WISPcloud back-end system and made available to the partners for access by API. After the trial period, the process of installation, maintenance, data collection and -processing and output provision was evaluated by the partners.

II. Scope

The scope of this document is to report on

- 1) the technical properties of the WISPstation instrument
- 2) the data requests possible through the API
- 3) the location and timing of the instrument installations
- 4) some preliminary results
- 5) a bundling of the results of the initial evaluation of the installed instrument

III. The technical properties of the WISPstation instrument

Several essentially different viewing geometry designs for above water optical systems have been proposed in literature such as:

- a) The sun-following design with one-radiometer (Seaprism, (Zibordi et al., 2009)), or with 3 radiometers, Dalec: (Brando et al., 2016))
- b) The one viewing angle 2 radiometers system with the Lup sensor under water ((Lee, Ahn, Mobley, & Arnone, 2010))
- c) The two (or more) fixed viewing angles system (Wernand, 2002, Tilstone et al., 2002)

Basis for designs a) and c) are the considerations by (Mobley, 1999), namely azimuth angle is optimal around 138 degrees from the sun, Lup angle is around 42 degrees from the nadir and Lsky angle is around 42 degrees from the zenith. With varying geometry, Mobley proposes a table of coefficients to account for surface reflections at various wind speeds and solar position.

The WISPstation is based on a modification of the Wernand design using two sets of sensors looking NNW and NNE instead of NW and NE. It should preferably be installed looking in a northward direction (on the Northern hemisphere) providing two optimal viewing geometry moments during the day and a large time window with acceptable viewing geometries that can be accounted for. The advantage of a fixed system with two viewing directions is that there are no moving parts, robots etc. which makes the system less costly, better to maintain and less prone to malfunctions.

In total the WISPstation features 8 channels:

- 2 Radiance channels collecting L_{up} and L_{sky} in the NNW direction
- 2 Radiance channels collecting L_{up} and L_{sky} in the NNE direction
- 2 Irradiance channels
- 1 unexposed dark radiance channel for evaluation of radiance channel degradation
- 1 unexposed dark irradiance channel for evaluation of the degradation of irradiance channels

All channels are connected to the central spectrometer by means of optical fibres and an optical multiplexer. The advantage of this design is, amongst others, that any variability or degradation of the sensitivity of the spectrometer is compensated in the calculation of remote sensing reflectance. A regular measurement cycle where each channel is measured 10 times at an optimal integration time takes usually less than 1 minute depending on ambient light conditions. The system is calibrated relative to a reference instrument. The reference instrument is calibrated in a certified laboratory using a lamp and integrating sphere with NIST traceable calibrations.

The WISPstation is water tight and built into a highly climate resistant case. Temperature of the sensor and humidity in the case is registered along with every measurement. Data are transmitted to the database ("WISPcloud") autonomously through a cellular connection. The instrument can be remotely accessed and e.g. updated or configured to a specific time interval or measurement frequency. It is autonomously powered by a solar panel and internal large battery.

Figure 1: Layout and installation of a WISPstation

Currently the WISPstation is built around the Avantes Mini mk-1 spectrometer with a maximum wavelength range between 220 and 1100 nm. The grating has 300 lines per mm with a blaze of 300 nm. Together with a slit of 100 μm this leads to a spectral resolution (FWHM) of 4.65 nm. Stray light is reported to be lower than 0.2%. The WISPstation spectral characteristics are to some extent configurable. The Avantes Mini is a rugged spectrometer designed for use outside of laboratories. Serial production by assembly robots warranty very small differences between instruments. While the standard measurement frequency is set to once per 15 minutes, it can be increased to once per two minutes if required, e.g. in intervals around satellite overpasses.

The most important characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Specifications of the WISPstation:	
Wavelength range :	Max: 220-1100 nm (depends on calibration)
Channels	
5 Radiance channels:	2 * Lup and 2 * Lsky (both sensor sets look at opposite angles away from the sun):
3 Irradiance channels:	2 * upward looking
Unexposed reference dark channels:	1 * radiance and 1* irradiance
Physical characteristics	
Grating: Lines per mm: 300	Blaze (nm): 300
Slit: 100 μm	FWHM (at 100 μm slit, 300 lines / mm): 4.65 nm
Stray light: <0.2%	Signal/Noise: Min 300:1
AD converter: 16 Bit 2MHz	Integration time: 1.05 ms to max 10 minutes
Temperature range: 0-55C	Powering: Independent: solar panel
Internet Connectivity: 2 Way over 3G or WIFI	Pole size for attaching the instrument: 5 – 10 cm diameter
Measurements	
Measurement frequency: 1x per 15 minutes (adjustable)	Repetitions: Each channel is read out 10 times
Output: Quality controlled Rrs(0+) at 1 nm	

Table 1 Specifications of the WISPstation

IV. Database and output API

A scalable Postgres database (WISPcloud) is available to autonomously receive and store all measurements, to perform quality control, to apply water quality algorithms and to serve data requests directly to customers through an advanced API. Internal quality control procedures are increasingly being put into place to identify and flag sub-optimal measurements.

Currently glint correction is handled in a basic way (fixed $\rho_{sky} = 0.028$), the results of research into advance options for glint correction (Groetsch et al., 2018) will be implemented soon.

For water quality monitoring purposes, the remote sensing reflectance observations are run through some standard water quality algorithms to make a first estimate of Chlorophyll-a (Gons, 1999), total suspended matter (Rijkeboer, 1999), Phycocyanin (Simis, 2005) and water transparency (Gons et al, 1998). For a short description of the API see **Error! Reference source not found.**

V. EOMORES demonstration installations of the WISPstation

During the 2nd year of the EOMORES project 5 WISPstations were installed at the following locations:

Instrument	Country	Location name	Latitude	Longitude	Start date of data collection
WISPstation001	Italy	Lake Trasimeno	43.1223	12.1344	24-4-2018
WISPstation003	Scotland	Loch Leven	56.1981	-3.3732	20-8-2018
WISPstation005	Estonia	Lake Võrtsjärv	58.2195	26.1074	2-6-2018
WISPstation006	Lithuania	Curonian Lagoon	55.4126	21.1002	16-8-2016
WISPstation007	Lithuania	Curonian Lagoon	55.7195	21.1016	16-8-2016

Table 2 EOMORES installations of the WISPstations

V.1. WISPstation001: Lake Trasimeno, Italy

Installation on: fixed platform
Installation date: 24-04-2018
Location: Lake Trasimeno Italy
Project: EOMORES
Partner: CNR
User: Arpa Umbria

Figure 2 Location information and photograph of WISPstation001

V.2. WISPstation003: Loch Leven, Schotland

Installation on: small buoy
 Installation date: 20-08-2018
 Location: Loch Leven
 Project: EOMORES

Figure 3 Location information and photograph of WISPstation003

V.3. WISPstation005: Lake Võrtsjärv, Estonia

Installation on: fixed platform
 Installation date: 02-06-2018
 Location: Lake Võrtsjärv Estonia
 Project: EOMORES

Figure 4 Location information and photograph of WISPstation005

V.4. WISPstation006 and 007: Curonian Lagoon, Lithuania

Installation on: Pole (2 instruments)
Installation date: 16-08-2018
Location: Klaipėda, Lithuania
Project: EOMORES

Figure 5 Location information and photograph of WISPstation006

VI. Some preliminary results

Figure 6 typical spectra of WISPstation001

Figure 7: time series of standard water quality parameters at WISPstation001

Typical reflectance spectra (Figure 6) measured by WISPstation001 in Lake Trasimeno show a clear evolution from April to September 2018. In April there is hardly any Chlorophyll-a development in the water and no absorption dip around 676 nm. From month to month this absorption dip increases. Gradually also some influence of phycocyanin is visible as an absorption dip around 620 nm. The spectrum seems to be strongly influenced by CDOM absorption since the blue part of the spectrum below 550 nm is taken away by absorption. The time series of standard water quality parameters (Figure 7) confirm this. There is a clear increase of Chlorophyll-a during the summer, accompanied by an increase in phycocyanin late summer.

WISPstation003, placed in Loch Leven, had to be sent back and forth for a repair, hence a part of the time series is missing (Figure 8). The time series shows that after a peak in Chlorophyll-a concentration in August the concentrations decline. TSM and transparency are more or less constant. It will have to be evaluated if the standard algorithms apply for this Loch.

Figure 8: time series of standard water quality parameters at WISPstation003

Figure 9: typical spectra at WISPstation005

Figure 10: time series of standard water quality parameters at WISPstation005

Lake Vörtsjärv is known to be heavily dominated by organic matter, both as suspended and as dissolved fraction. This is clear from the spectra as measured by the WISPstation005 (Figure 9). Typical absorption valleys of Chlorophyll-a and phycocyanin are present over the whole time period, whereby especially the Chlorophyll-a dip deepens during the summer. This is reflected by the time series plot (Figure 10) that indicates that Chlorophyll-a concentrations increase until well into September. Phycocyanin concentrations are low but exhibit a small increase in September. TSM and transparency show some interesting variability over periods of a few days to a week. Also in this case it needs to be confirmed if the standard algorithms are applicable to this area.

Figure 11: typical spectra at WISPstation006

Figure 12: time series of standard water quality parameters at WISPstation006

WISPstations006 and 007 were placed in the Curonian Lagoon in Lithuania. Their spectra are very influenced by Chlorophyll-a and phycocyanin absorption (Figure 11). The time series (Figure 12 and Figure 13) indicate that the concentrations of both algae pigments are much higher than at the other locations (note the vertical scales). While the within day variability at WISPstation006 is very high, this is not the case for WISPstation007. These differences need to be investigated further.

The WISPstations001 (Lake Trasimeno), 005 (Lake Vörtsjärv) and 006 (Curonian Lagoon) have measured without problems. WISPstations001 experienced a communication issue (3g/4g) at the end of the season, but the software includes a mitigation strategy for such situations, during which the data should be stored in the local database. They will be recovered after the instrument is back in the office. WISPstations003 and 007 had an unfortunate unique breakdown of a component, for which it had to be sent back for repairs. Except for the repair periods the instruments have been measuring automatically.

Besides confirmation of the reflectance and water quality parameters by validation it is necessary to address the following two issues:

- 1) It must be investigated what is the cause of the within-day variability of spectra and water quality parameters, and possibly compensate it. Sun- and sky glint is probably a potential cause.
- 2) It must be investigated to what extent the “standard algorithms” applied in this phase are suitable/representative for the various locations and watertypes.

VII. Summary of questionnaire results

The four partners who had a WISPstation provided a first technical evaluation of the WISPstations by means of filling in a questionnaire. Also a partner that did not have a WISPstation but worked with the data filled out a questionnaire, reviewing the API access. Some condensed results of the questionnaire are:

The instruments have been installed on remote locations, 4 on a pole and 1 on a small buoy. The locations were chosen to give an unobstructed view on the water surface and at locations relative secure from vandalism. For mounting the instruments on poles the weight is ok, for the buoy it was too heavy.

Some instruments had performance issues which could be fixed at Water Insight. It was suggested to allow repairs at the location. This is being considered but may be difficult since it will void the calibration.

Most of the installations were done by or supported at the location by a Water Insight employee. Partners consider that a next installation can be done by themselves.

Protection of the optics during transport was ok, but protection of the upward looking irradiance sensors should be improved to prevent birds sitting and fouling the sensors. (spikes were suggested).

Maintenance was difficult for the remote locations but is being considered for the next season (sensor cleaning).

The fixed position set-up with one set of sensors looking at the NNW and one set of sensors looking at the NNE was assessed ok, but suggestions were made to make the sensor rotating to follow the sun. This is an essential change of design which will not be followed up.

It should be tested if the instrument stays in the pre-set horizontal position after a period. It was noted that the buoy may have rotated slightly, but the instrument does not measure that, nor does the buoy.

By opening a lid, users can see the status of the instrument from LED coloured messages. After installation it proved difficult to remove the lid to inspect the status. It was done once in the field and provided valuable status information.

The solar panel is a convenient power source but might have increased capacity during longer periods of low light conditions. One of the very interesting outcomes of the demonstrations is that partners like to be able to continue measuring as long as possible during autumn and winter.

Autonomous data transfer over 3g/4g is evaluated as very positive, as well as automatic storage of the measurements in the WISPcloud backend system. Data can be retrieved manually and by script from the API which (after some studying) provides a good and easy access to the data. The output format is ok. Adding a quick viewer to the latest measurements was suggested.

Although the standard measurement interval of 15 minutes is ok, partners would like higher frequency observations around satellite overpasses.

First evaluations show that the quality of the reflectance data is very good. Evaluation of the water quality parameters is ongoing. Attention should be given to the quality of the data around low sun elevations. CDOM is a requested additional parameter. It should be evaluated if various locations would require specific algorithms.

Partners would find a field (quick) charging device and a field calibration unit very interesting. Also the addition of a weather station and a water temperature sensor is very interesting.

Overall the partners report that they are happy to very happy with the instrument and the support by Water Insight (one case medium). It is evaluated as positive that the instrument does not suffer from under water fouling which is a serious problem when using e.g. fluoroprobes. Installation on a small buoy provides the most challenging situation.

Some partners also provided useful and positive information on the willingness to obtain the instrument after the project and the conditions.

VIII. Conclusions

During EOMORES, five WISPstations were installed at various places in Europe. Four instruments were installed on a pole and one on a buoy. Spectra collected by the instruments look very plausible but within day variations have to be looked into. After the measurement season partners were asked to evaluate the systems by filling in a questionnaire. The results were in general very positive. A specific point of attention is the prevention of fouling of the top irradiance sensors and investigating the possibility of regular cleaning of the lenses. In the coming period the spectral measurements will be compared to measurements from other systems. Water quality results will be validated by regular in-situ samples and it will be established if the pre-programmed “standard” water quality algorithms are representative for the lakes under consideration.

References

- Brando, V., Lovell, J, King, E., Boadle, D., Scott, R., Schroeder, T. (2016) The Potential of Autonomous Ship-Borne Hyperspectral Radiometers for the Validation of Ocean Color Radiometry Data, Remote Sensing, 2016.
- CEOS. 2017. A. G. Dekker and N. Pinnel, editors. Feasibility study for an aquatic ecosystem Earth observing system. Report v. 1.1. Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) and Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organization (CSIRO). CSIRO, Canberra, ACT, Australia.
- Gons, H., 1999. Optical Teledetection of Chlorophyll a in turbid inland waters. Environ. Sci. Technol. 33, pp. 1127-1132
- Gons, H.J., Ebert, J., Kromkamp, J. 1998. Optical teledetection of the vertical attenuation coefficient for downward quantum irradiance of photosynthetically available radiation in turbid inland waters. Aquatic Ecology 31, pp. 299–311
- Groetsch, P.M.; Gege, P.; Simis, S.G.; Eleveld, M.A.; Peters, S.W. Validation of a spectral correction procedure for sun and sky reflections in above-water reflectance measurements. *Opt. Express* **2017**, 25, A742–A761.
- Hommersom, A., Kratzer, S., Laanen, M. L., Ansko, I., Ligi, M., Bresciani, M., ... Peters, S. W. M. (2012). Intercomparison in the field between the new WISP-3 and other radiometers (TriOS Ramses, ASD FieldSpec, and TACCS). *Journal of Applied Remote Sensing*, 6, 06315-1-06315-21. DOI: 10.1117/1.JRS.6.063615
- Mobley, C. D. , 1999. Estimation of the remote-sensing reflectance from above-surface measurements. *Appl. Opt.* 38(36), 7442–7455, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1364/AO.38.007442.APOPAI0003-6935>
- Rijkeboer, M., Pasterkamp, R., Peters, S. 1999. Voorbereidende studie voor de implementatie van een spectroradiometrische veldmeetmethode voor het monitoren van optische waterkwaliteitsparameters. IVM Report O-99/09, 56 pp.
- Simis, S.G.H., Peters S.W.M., Gons, H.J., 2005. Remote sensing of the cyanobacterial pigment phycocyanin in turbid inland water. *Limnol. Oceanogr.*, 50(1), pp. 237–245
- Tilstone, G. and G. Moore, eds. REVAMP Regional Validation of MERIS Chlorophyll products in North Sea coastal waters: Protocols document. 2002
- Wernand M.R. Guidelines for (Ship-Borne) Auto-Monitoring of Coastal and Ocean Colour. In: Ackleson S.G., Trees C., editors. Proceedings of Ocean Optics XVI; Santa Fe, NM, USA. 18– 22 November 2002; <http://melia.nioz.nl/phptoweb/colors/documentation/colours38.htm>
- ZhongPing Lee, Yu-Hwan Ahn, Curtis Mobley, and Robert Arnone. (2010). Removal of surface-reflected light for the measurement of remote-sensing reflectance from an above-surface platform. *OPTICS EXPRESS*. 6 December 2010 / Vol. 18, No. 25 / 26313-26324
- Zibordi, G., Holben, B., Slutsker, I., Giles, D., D’Alimonte, D., Melin, F., Berthon, J.-F., Vandemark, D., Feng, H., Schuster, G., Fabbri, B. E., Kaitala, S., and Seppala, J.: AERONET-OC: a network for the validation of Ocean Color primary radiometric products, *J. Atmos. Oc. Technol.*, 26, 1634–1651, 2009

IX. Annexes

IX.1. Annex I: Description of data queries through the API

IX.1.1. General requests

To receive information or data from WISPcloud one must formulate a request. The request can be done manually in a browser or can be a part of a script.

The basic form of the request is:

```
https:wispcloud.waterinsight.nl/api/query?SERVICE=data
```

The request can be expanded to ask for documentation:

```
https:wispcloud.waterinsight.nl/api/query?SERVICE=Data&VERSION=1.0&REQUEST=GetDocumentation
```

To see if measurements are arriving at the database, issue the ShowRecent request to make the server send back a list of the 30 measurements most recent measurements in the database.

```
https:wispcloud.waterinsight.nl/api/query?SERVICE=data&VERSION=1.0&REQUEST=ShowRecent
```

To request data or information about the instrument/location (metadata) issue the GetData is used:

```
https:wispcloud.waterinsight.nl/api/query?SERVICE=Data&VERSION=1.0&REQUEST=GetData
```

Without any further arguments the GetData request provides the following information:

```
instrument.name  
measurement.date  
measurement.id  
waterquality.tsm  
waterquality.chla  
waterquality.kd
```

Without adding the level2.quality request, GetData only displays those datasets that pass the internal quality control done by WISPcloud.

The GetData request accepts the **TIME**, **BBOX**, **INSTRUMENT** and **MEASUREMENT** arguments to narrow down a query.

Additionally this request accepts the **INCLUDE** argument to define which fields are to be returned and in what order.

The full list of INCLUDE arguments available to GetData are still evolving as we e.g. add new algorithms.

The service is written to happily keep sending results to the requesting client until done, but for most practical purposes we strongly recommend limiting the scope of your request to a narrow window of time and location to keep down the size of the results! This is critically important when you view the results in a web browser rather than saving them directly to file, because it is very easy to make a web browser (which wants to cache the file it is displaying) run completely out of memory! Using a tool like curl to pull something from the api straight into a file on disk should be safe.

IX.1.2. Measurement fields

MEASUREMENT fields that can be queried using the **INCLUDE** argument:

date	# Alias for measurement.date
lat	# Alias for measurement.latitude
lon	# Alias for measurement.longitude
measurement	# Alias for measurement.id
measurement.date	# Date and time of the measurement
measurement.id	# Unique identifier for this measurement
measurement.owner	# Names the account that owns this measurement, if there is a defined data owner

IX.1.3. Instrument fields

INSTRUMENT Information (including where it is set up (and facing))

instrument.name	# The common name of the instrument
instrument.type	# The instrument type/family
measurement.latitude	# Latitude in degrees
measurement.longitude	# Longitude in degrees
site.azimuth	# Azimuth angle describing the facing of the instrument on its site
site.campaign	# Campaign for this the instrument was at this site (optional)
site.name	# Site name (optional)
site.region	# Site region (optional)
site.station	# Identifier of the station onto which the instrument was installed (optional)

The WISPstation has four channels with lenses measuring radiance. Two channels look up to measure the downwelling (sky) radiance. Two channels look down to measure the upwelling radiance (u=upwelling, d=downwelling). Four fields can be queried to give the relative azimuth angle of the lens viewing direction with respect to the azimuthal orientation of the instrument (site.azimuth).

ldp.channel.orientation	# portside Ld channel: relative viewing azimuth angle
lds.channel.orientation	# starboardside Ld channel: relative viewing angle
lup.channel.orientation	# portside Ld channel: relative viewing azimuth angle
lus.channel.orientation	# starboardside Ld channel: relative viewing angle

p=portside location (left when looking to the bow of a ship), s=starboardside location (right when looking to the bow of a ship). Notice that because the lensholder is inset rather than protruding, the channels are in a 'cross-eyed' configuration. This means that the portside sensors are looking to the NNE and the starboard sensors are looking to the NNW if the instrument itself is facing North.

IX.1.4. Level 1 data

Ed channels measure irradiance, Ld and Lu channels measure radiance.

ed.irradiance	# Radiometrically corrected sky irradiance
ed.quality	# Summarizes flags as okay, suspect or invalid
ed.selected	# Tells which Ed channel was used
ld.radiance	# Radiometrically corrected downwelling radiance
ld.quality	# Summarizes flags as okay, suspect or invalid
ld.selected	# Tells which Ld channel was used
lu.radiance	# Radiometrically corrected upwelling radiance
lu.quality	# Summarizes flags as okay, suspect or invalid
lu.selected	# Tells which Lu channel was used

E.g.: <https://wispcloud.waterinsight.nl/api/query?SERVICE=Data&VERSION=1.0&REQUEST=GetData&INCLUDE=lu.radiance>

The WISPcloud processing automatically selects the set of radiance channels that have the most optimal relative viewing angles. One can query a specific radiance channel by adding p or s (e.g. Ldp).

There are two Ed sensors each on top of the instrument. WISPcloud automatically selects the Ed sensor with the highest output for further calculations. To explicitly choose which channel's data you want to see, you can replace the generic name with the specific channel name, e.g.:

eda.irradiance	# Radiometrically corrected upwelling radiance using aft Ed channel
edf.irradiance	# Radiometrically corrected upwelling radiance using front Ed channel

The coding is also in ships terminology: a = aft = towards the rear and f = fore = towards the front.

*It is important to recognize that **INCLUDE** parameters are only about what is displayed, not which way the calculation goes. Including explicitly the data from certain channels in your output does NOT make those the channels used in the reflectance and subsequent water quality calculations! It only means you have the option to also see what was in the channel not used in the calculation.*

IX.1.5. Level 1B data

Every channel is measured 10 times consecutively. It is possible to query for a listing of spectra at level 1b, the per channel, per repeat (ir)radiances. Queries that return a complete spectrum will return a substantial volume of data on every row, and as there are typically sixty level 1b spectra on just the measurement channels (10 repeats on six channels), it also returns a lot of rows per measurement.

Please contact Water Insight to help you formulate your L1B request and assist you with interpreting the results (since this will generate a very large amount of results)!

IX.1.6. Level 2 data

level2.quality
level2.reflectance #remote sensing reflectance assuming rho=0.028

Important: Including the level2.quality parameter does two things:

- 1) It adds the quality information column to the output
- 2) we assume that explicitly requesting the quality implies that the user is aware of the possible different quality levels of data. Therefore, it also makes visible all the records in your result set where the quality is below the standard of quality that is shown by default.

IX.1.7. Water quality parameters

chla
cpc
kd
tsm
waterquality.chla
waterquality.chla.gons
waterquality.cpc
waterquality.cpc.simis
waterquality.kd
waterquality.kd.gons
waterquality.tsm
waterquality.tsm.rijkeboer

E.g. <https://wispcloud.waterinsight.nl/api/query?SERVICE=Data&VERSION=1.0&REQUEST=GetData&INCLUDE=chl>

IX.1.8. Filtering the request to space, time or instrument number

Without providing a space/time/instrument filter the database produces the latest 100 measurements satisfying the request parameters. To narrow down a query several arguments are possible:

The requests for L1, L1B, L2 and Water quality parameters accept the TIME, BBOX, INSTRUMENT and MEASUREMENT arguments to narrow down a query.

BBOX:

The BBOX argument is a cleaner way to geographically limit results to those from measurements taken within a certain extent, by using one or more spatial envelopes in lat/lon coordinates. If omitted, measurements from anywhere will be shown (including those with NULL values in their location field).

The format for the argument is BBOX=<west edge longitude>, <south edge latitude>, <east edge longitude>, <north edge latitude>

If the BBOX parameter is specified more than once, records from either area will be included. Uniqueness of records in the output set is preserved, so when areas overlap, records in the overlap area are only added to the result set once.

The following would select instruments in the area of Lake Trasimeno, Italy (approximately at least, as the example simplifies the bounding extent to 1 decimal place. You can of course provide more precision)

<https:wispcloud.waterinsight.nl/api/query?SERVICE=data&VERSION=1.0&REQUEST=GetData&BBOX=12.0,43.0,12.2,43.2>

TIME

The TIME argument allows for limiting output to a time interval, using two ISO timestamps separated by a comma.

Similar to the BBOX argument, if it is provided more than once, results matching EITHER range are returned, e.g. adding these parameters will select measurements from between 9:00 and 19:00 on the 11th and 16th of May 2018.

<https:wispcloud.waterinsight.nl/api/query?SERVICE=data&VERSION=1.0&REQUEST=GetData&TIME=2018-05-11T09:00,2018-05-11T19:00&TIME=2018-05-16T09:00,2018-05-16T19:00>

INSTRUMENT

The INSTRUMENT argument allows retrieving only results from a set of known instruments.

The instrument argument can be given using either the instrument's name (e.g. WISPstation004), the instrument's serial number (e.g. 6701-0004-0000-0000) or the instrument's database id (e.g. 24)

<https:wispcloud.waterinsight.nl/api/query?SERVICE=data&VERSION=1.0&REQUEST=GetData&INSTRUMENT=WISPstation002>

You can indicate more than one instrument by having putting the INSTRUMENT parameter in your query multiple times with different values, or by passing it a comma separated list. These are equivalent:

<https:wispcloud.waterinsight.nl/api/query?SERVICE=data&VERSION=1.0&REQUEST=GetData&INSTRUMENT=WISPstation002,WISPstation003,WISPstation004>

<https:wispcloud.waterinsight.nl/api/query?SERVICE=data&VERSION=1.0&REQUEST=GetData&INSTRUMENT=WISPstation002&INSTRUMENT=WISPstation003&INSTRUMENT=WISPstation004>